

An Introduction to the Xperi Driving Simulation Environment: Hardware, Software and Data Acquisition

Rachel Corcoran, Paul Kielty, Padraic Toomey, Maciej Stec and Joe Lemley,
Xperi, Galway, Ireland

Abstract

In this paper details are given on the Driving Simulation Environment system developed by Xperi and how it is used for a large-scale data acquisition for driving drowsiness studies. The data collected includes RGB, NIR and thermal video data, audio data (speech and paralinguistic elements such as yawns), and several biosignals from a human participant in a simulated driving environment. This set of biosignals contains electroencephalography (EEG), heart rate, blood oxygen level, breathing rate, eye-motion and blink data, temperature, and galvanic skin response. The experimental protocol involves completing a number of tests and simulated driving sessions at fixed times over a 24-hour period, with rest periods where participants can eat, watch movies, read, or otherwise entertain themselves. However, they are not allowed to sleep or consume any stimulants or depressants during the data acquisition. A key goal is to develop machine vision algorithms that can detect human cognitive, emotional and drowsiness states from non-contact video data. Operational details and procedural aspects of the data acquisition are given. This paper compliments the training workshop run at IMVIP 2023.

Keywords: Driving Simulation, Image Processing, Machine Vision, Driver Monitoring, Data Acquisition.

1 Introduction

It is estimated that tired drivers are the cause of 1 in 5 road collisions every year in Ireland (Pires et al. 2020; Commission 2021). When a driver starts to tire their reactions slow and eventually, they begin to exhibit microsleeps or even fall asleep at the wheel. The introduction of driver monitoring systems (DMS) will mitigate the associated risks but requires a better understanding of how drowsiness manifests in different individuals and can be identified via non-contact solutions such as image/video-based sensing (Albadawi, Takruri, and Awad 2022; Cardone et al. 2021; Jahan et al. 2023). Xperi is a world leader in DMS technologies and is currently undertaking a large-scale data study on 500 human participants to improve the sensing capabilities of DMS technologies. A training workshop will be presented at IMVIP 2023 for delegates who wish to learn about the data acquisition techniques and learn from the experience of the Xperi team in this field.

This short paper provides complimentary information on the rationale and basis for this study and some details on the driving simulation environment (DSE) that is used at Xperi to conduct these studies. It will also provide an overview of the software, sensors and protocols used to gather data in the DSE. The importance of different data types is explained as well as the process of relating certain data to a participant's drowsiness state, which is detected using neuromorphic vision cameras. The data collected includes heart rate, neural signals, blood oxygen levels, body temperature, eye movements, self-assessment tests and respiration. These act as indicators of the cognitive and emotional state of a participant and confirm their level of drowsiness as detected by the driver monitoring software through event cameras. This allows for precise training of a range of advanced neural-network based machine vision algorithms.

2 The Driving Simulation Environment

2.1 Hardware and Control Subsystems

The Xperi DSE consists of a car interior set on an actuated platform and installed with a specialized driving simulator wheel, pedals, and gearstick. The steering wheel and pedals have force feedback for immersion. Three 49-inch monitors are configured as a continuous display and offer a wide field of view for rendered scenes in front of the simulator. For a display to run tests in parallel with the driving, a small additional monitor is mounted in front of the driver (but elevated for minimal obstruction of the display). The DSE equipment and software are controlled with one computer, with a separate computer used for collecting all video, audio, and physiological data. Other features of the DSE system that may need to be adjusted by technical staff are controlled using a keyboard/mouse interface. Note that the DSE has a complete seating arrangement to allow for studies with passengers and rear-seat occupants as well as driver-only studies. The simulator frame and dashboard provide mounting points for cameras and other equipment.

Figure 1(a): View of seating and immersive tri-screen display; blinds are drawn when the simulation is active.

Figure 1(b): Driver view with instrument cluster, steering wheel, pedal assembly and video acquisition systems

2.2 Driving Simulator Software

For an immersive driving experience, the DSE supports realistic driving video games *Assetto Corsa* and *EuroTruck Sim 2*. These offer highly configurable simulation environments providing customizability in terms of time of day, vehicle size, engine power, driving dynamics, braking capabilities, and other aspects of vehicle response. The software parameters are pre-set according to each driving scenario and are designed to provide study participants with a range of challenges of varying difficulty during each driving session. As their drowsiness level increases, they become more likely to make errors or fail in the assigned tasks. Custom software was developed for the simultaneous recording and monitoring of the camera feeds and biosignals.

3 Study Rationale and Data Type Selection

This study collects these multiple, complimentary video data streams, together with sensing data from a range of on-body biophysical sensors. The on-body sensor signals provide biophysical markers and biometric data that can characterise more specifically the cognitive, or emotional states of a human participant. These data are then used to annotate video data to provide a ground truth for training advanced machine vision models that may be incorporated into future generations of Driver Monitoring technology. The DMS in today's vehicles are often based on a near Infrared (NIR) video camera. This captures light across a broader range of wavelengths (up to 1500 nm) than a conventional video camera and thus performs better in the variable lighting conditions of a vehicle cabin. It can operate well both in strong sunlight and in night-time environments. However, there are several emerging imaging technologies which can provide different information that may be useful to tomorrow's

DMS. These include thermal imaging cameras based on uncooled bolometer technology which have become more competitive cost-wise in recent years, and event-cameras, sometimes referred to as neuromorphic vision systems, which instantly capture light-changes from individual pixels rather than accumulating a full image frame. Thermal imaging is based on the thermal emissivity of the human body and can provide very useful information on breathing patterns, facial blood flow and other physiological signals and operates independently from the lighting levels in the vehicle cabin. Event cameras detecting changes in individual pixel intensity provide much higher motion sensitivity and can track facial and eye-behaviours with higher temporal resolution than a video camera.

3.1 Data Types

Video and Audio Data: RGB, NIR, thermal and neuromorphic vision data are collected via a dedicated PC running custom acquisition software. Among other features, this software offers simultaneous displays of all cameras feeds and assigns a timestamp to each recorded frame. Capturing time-synchronized data is important to allow accurate annotation across data streams for the training of machine vision algorithms.

Biosignal Data and equipment: Biosignal data are captured primarily via the PLUX Biosignal Sensor Hub (Cardone et al. 2021; Jahan et al. 2023) supporting simultaneous acquisition across eight sensor channels. The following sensor types were selected for this study.

- Blood oxygen saturation levels are measured using SPO2 sensor.
- Heart rate is measured using a 3-electrode electrocardiography sensor.
- Eye motion and blink signals are measured using electrooculography.
- Temperature is measured with a thermistor secured directly on the forehead.
- Breathing rate is measured with an inductive respiration sensor.
- The galvanic skin response is measured with an electrodermal activity sensor on the palm

EEG across 32 channels is recorded with a [Neuroelectrics Enobio 32 EEG](#). EEG readings can be used to detect, for example, the onset of eye blinks, microsleeps and drowsiness levels. The change in electrical activity that occurs due to an eye blink is known as the Berger Effect, and it presents as an increased frequency of alpha waves in the prefrontal cortex (Kirschfield, Kuno, 2005).

Measuring Drowsiness Level: The participant completes 1-hour simulated driving sessions at 5 points throughout the 24 hours. Accompanying tests to quantify drowsiness level are performed directly before and after the driving blocks. These include the Psychomotor Vigilance Task (PVT) (Huang et al. 2020; Trotti et al. 2022), the Alpha Attenuation Test (AAT) (Stampi, Stone, and Michimori 1995), the Karolinska Sleepiness Scale (KSS) questionnaire, and observations of how well the participant is driving in the simulator (O’Callaghan et al. 2022). The PVT evaluates alertness and attentiveness by the participants reaction time. It is based on the participant’s reaction time to visual stimuli that occur at random intervals. The AAT requires the participant hold their eyes closed for 2 minutes, then eyes open for 2 minutes, and evaluates their drowsiness by the difference in EEG activity in the 8-12Hz (alpha) band between the two states. (Hussain et al. 2022; Jing et al. 2020; O’Callaghan et al. 2022). Self-annotations also describe the participant’s drowsiness level and are produced by the participants through KSS testing. When requested, the participant uses a tablet to indicate their drowsiness level on a scale from 1-9. Each value has a description, starting with “extremely alert” at 1 and finishing with “very sleepy, great effort to keep awake, fighting sleep” at 9. A value of 10 can also be assigned by the acquisition staff if the participant has fallen asleep when they should be completing the KSS questionnaire.

4 Data Acquisition Protocol

Participants for this study are recruited via an external agency. No later than 1 day before a participant’s scheduled acquisition, they are contacted to ensure full understanding of the acquisition and verify all consent forms have been read and signed. At any time in the 24-hour acquisition the participant can request to finish the study and will be compensated based on the time completed. An overview the first 6 hours of the study protocol is provided in table 1. The recording sequences are repeated at 3pm, 11pm, 3am and 4am.

Summary of Activity	Approximate Duration	Goals
Introduction to the Lab environment, technical staff; explanations and Q&A	30 minutes	Allow participant to get familiar with the lab, staff and to confirm understanding of study protocols and expectations.
Sensor application, signal quality checks, and DSE instruction.	1 hour	All health sensors are applied and the quality of all biosignals and camera outputs is checked. The participant is instructed on the DSE and given time to practice driving.
Recording sequence #1: Drowsiness tests and 1 hour of driving; run remotely by technicians.	1.5 hours	Drowsiness level measured with AAT, PVT, and KSS before and after 1 hour of simulated driving. All cameras and sensors are recording throughout.
Driving without visible sensors. run remotely by technicians.	30 minutes	Sensors visible to the cameras are removed for another 15 minutes of driving. This generates data to verify camera-based algorithms are not using visible sensor features.
Break	2.5 hours	Remaining sensors removed and participant has a break.

Table 1: Initial 6-hour cycle of the study protocol

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